

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Abdelgadir**FIRST NAME:** Gawahir**PROGRAM CODE:** DIPH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** One (1)**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
4. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)
5. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 49-55)
7. Quotation Marks (EUCLID 2019, 6-7)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I have practiced writing essays since high schools, undergraduate, and graduate years. I wrote my bachelor's and master's thesis of dissertation and research. It was a great challenge finding yourself in front of a large amount of data and information needed to be manipulated to have a convincing discussion and a good result ending with an accommodating conclusion. As a result, I gained experience and skills in writing. However, is EUCLID's paper writing a different concept rather than the information that I have? Period (1) in ACA-401D consists of study materials of course pack, video on rules of style for a Response Paper (RP). The ACA-401D period (1) coursepack and the video explained the course mission and prepared and provided me with the suitable articles that refine my knowledge. These articles are significant for answering and analyzing my question, thesis expansion, topic research, and results presented throughout my studies besides, they clench my future career. Writing a RP should be properly done which means the essay will be evaluated not only based on ideas, but also by the quality of writing. There is an obvious difference between writing a good essay for general classes and writing an essay for an

ACA- 401D course. After all, the key concepts and strategies are the most important things to know what should be written in advance.

2) SUCCESSFUL ESSAY BASICS

The first chapter of the ACA-401D period one (1) acquaints the basics of essay writing. Generally, essays have three main parts; introduction, body and conclusion however, academic essay depends on the course requirement. The most important part of the essay is the central idea. An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence it should answer a question or a task (EUCLID 2019, 1). When I write an essay I should provide necessary background information. A thesis statement answers the question, in addition, reasoning and evidence will develop the thesis argument (ibid). Is clear that the relevant examples support the statement with evidence from academic texts or credible sources, where the thesis statement serves as a roadmap. In education, teachers have to pass CBEST (California Basics Education Skills Test).

In the **CBEST** test, you are given two **essay** prompts: The Writing test consists of two **essay** questions. One of the **essay** questions asks examinees to write about a remembered experience. The other question is designed to elicit expository prose that will permit writers to demonstrate their analytic skills (**CBEST** 2013). Ultimately, it was my experience as a teacher that sharpened me to write a successful academic essay. But honestly, a scientific essay is my favorite style because it is convincing, and I could provide facts and information that I gained throughout my specialization as a researcher and so far as a scientist. Scientific researches that concern public health, figure out the most important results and findings to come out with useful conclusions. These conclusions contribute to solving global health problems. Papers that present research results must be written in organized essays with basics of argumentum ideas and logical and supportive examples.

3) PLGIARISM

The UNC Honor System defines plagiarism as "the deliberate or reckless representation of another's words, thoughts, or ideas as one's own without attribution in connection with submission of academic work, whether graded or otherwise" (<https://guides.lib.unc.edu/plagiarism-citing>).

The way that some students copied others work indicates either they are struggling in writing or they want to get good grade for high competition (Harris 2020). However, in order to avoid plagiarism, the solution is to properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using (EUCLID 2019, 6).

As a science teacher, I have to access websites for scientific facts, so I do not need to cite for copying and pasting some relevant information especially if it concerns rules and common knowledge. But, when my students prepare their projects, I direct them to use trusted sites and have to put the link to avoid plagiarism. Schools' Textbooks provide enough materials for teachers and students to get the information that concerns the subjects.

In addition, some sources with links permit teachers and students to access for useful tools and more videos that explain experiments or create argument statements for classes, so teachers and students create accounts to help them to log in and react with the “Jam board” materials.

As a graduate student in EUCLID, when I write a paper response, I will have been using EUCLID basic rules in essays writing and to avoid plagiarism I went through the definition of plagiarism and the examples that EUCLID discussed in ACA-401D. Similarly, using acceptable phrases and paraphrases in citation. In paraphrase, I must use my own expressions and words, accurate knowledge and original writing of the author then I cite the information (EUCLID 2019, 8). In contrast, starting with the author’s name before the citation and adding only the page number between parentheses will modulate what is known as signal phrase (EUCLID 2019, 10).

4) STYLE GUIDE

The *Turabian style* is a citing and referencing system based on the *Chicago style* and named after Kate Turabian, from the University of Chicago, who authored a manual to guide students in citing and referencing when writing research papers. (guides.lib.monash.edu).

Two styles for citation are found in Turabian Manual: author-date style and notes-bibliography style, which are known as Chicago-manual of Style (Turabian 2020). Dr. Abel Scribe explained the two styles in chapter 8: CMS Crib Sheet of the course pack (EUCLID 2019, 44).

The official guide for me and for all writers to apply Chicago style is Turabian’s Manual. Chicago Notes are arranged in the order cited. In addition these Notes are commonly single spaced. However, citation in a text will be after punctuation at the end of the sentence. Citation of multiple references may be combined in the endnote or footnote (EUCLID 2019, 49,53).

Capitalization of words is the using of capital or, upper- case, letter. Accordingly, capitalization has three forms: full caps is to capitalize every letter in every word in main headings. The second form is heading caps which is to capitalize the first letter only in every word with some exceptions. The third form is the sentence caps (EUCLID 2019, 45).

The Chicago Manual of Style has discussed and given many examples of capitalization of foreign names and titles, ethnics or racial groups, and geographical names (ibid). Quotations are used in essay writing to avoid plagiarism because it gives a room for the writer to announce a citation and keeps the right for what someone else has said if the writer uses a phrase or a piece of work to support his argument and discussion. Each quotation needs to include a citation indicating author, year, and page number. In EUCLID, 2019 Scribe mentioned that the rule of Chicago Manual Style “of at least eight lines quotes set off as a block quotation” (CMS 2003, 447). In contrast, the APA directs the writers to use quotation for less than forty words (EUCLID 2019, 47).

5) LATIN EXPRESSIONS AND ABBREVIATIONS

I am still remembering my English teacher in middle school. One day when he was explaining a page in our literature book, he came across a paragraph that ended with etc. I wondered what that abbreviation meant. However, I raised my hand to ask him this question. He was so smart that he realized my question before I asked. He started to speak about Latin language and how ancient people used this language to register and document many conventions and treaties. He mentioned that the reason for using this language for it is permanent and never changes. In the faculty of science during my undergraduate studies, I had a course of scientific classification in biology, scientists used Latin words to classify animals and plants, so I got familiar with most of the abbreviations and Latin expressions and some of them are still used in English writing. Gene/gen comes from the Latin word meaning “born” or “produce.” I used in my research a lot of Latin and scientific words and expressions.

I used in my research- resisting insulin, and Leptin to detect the level of these hormones in diabetic women, also these hormones are of Latin words expressions. What I want to say here is that I am well known for dead language words. We used some of them daily like A.M (ante meridiem) that means before noon, P.M (post meridiem) means after noon, (Vice Versa) which means the other way round and e.g. (exempli gratia) stands for “for instance, or for example” (EUCLID 2019, 56,57, and 58). All these expressions are extensively used in scientific research medical fields and engineering.

When I prepared my CV for career and some applications, I used this abbreviation (Curriculum Vitae). In the USA they changed it into a new abbreviation which is “Resume” when I saw this abbreviation in EUCLID 2019 on page 56, I remembered and took me years back.

6) QUOTATION MARKS

a) Quotations

Quotations are the exact words the author has to be cited between quotation marks “.....” Quotations could be divided into two forms: short quotations, are of short paragraph and long quotations are quotations of more than four lines and they are without quotation marks (EUCLID 2019, 6, 7). Block quotations are not only introduced with punctuation appropriate to the syntax but also followed by commentary. Straight and curly quotations marks are used universally.

b) How to Write Footnotes and Referencing

Footnotes are notes or references written at the bottom or end of an essay that cite authors names, references name and the year in which the work has been registered or

published. However, footnotes are of two types: the quote style using parenthesis or in the foot area using the standard format (EUCLID 2019, 12).

7) CONCLUSION

Is not easy to write a response paper on different unlinked parts and each one has variant information. But, I felt that it was a challenge as it was my first response paper in my PhD in International Public Health (DIPH). I experienced in this course skills from the presented video by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck, reading of the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack and the documents accompanied the orientation session. Honestly, I need this foundation to step forward in writing responses in the different courses through my study as a PhD student. Avoiding plagiarism was the most important part in the coursepack. Using Grammarly will let me feel confident about writing without mistakes as well as following *Turabian style* and paraphrases according to EUCLID rules. I knew that most of the scientific expressions are of “Latin language” and this comforted me because it was my concern since I was an undergraduate student.

I could say now I am ready with my” forearm funneled and attached to the paddle.”

REFERENCES

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